

CHARACTERISTICS OF A PIEZOCOMPOSITE GENERATING ELEMENT

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1 Introduction

In this paper, we investigate performance and characteristics of a Piezocomposite Generating Element (PCGE) [1] which is composed of layers of carbon/epoxy, PZT ceramic, and glass/epoxy cured at an elevated temperature. In the experiment with vibrator, the PCGE performs as a secondary beam element in order to generate the electric power. The results of battery charging by using the PCGE in small scale wind mill [2] shows that the potential application of the PCGE in wind energy harvesting.

2 Design of wind energy harvesting device

2.1 The PCGE

According to Tien and Goo [1], the PCGE-A, which is shown in fig 1, demonstrates the best power generating performance among the other PCGEs. For the wind energy harvesting prototype, we choose the PCGE-A as a secondary vibrating beam element.

Fig. 1. The PCGE.

2.2 The energy harvesting device

The wind harvesting includes several components as in fig. 2. The acrylic frame is to connect the other parts. When the fan blade rotates under the wind force, the rotation is transferred to the rotary disk through the center rod. The exciter teeth excite the PCGE, which is clamped on the frame, through the mechanical interface where the

exciters contact the beam. When the PCGE is vibrated in the form of bending, it produces the electrical power.

In order to reduce the resonance frequency, a small steel tip mass ($12 \times 10 \times 10$ mm³; 9.36 gram) is attached to the tip of the beam.

Fig.2. The wind energy harvesting device.

3 Experiment set up

3.1 Voltage generating test with vibrator

We do the voltage generating test under excitation of vibrator in order to understand about the voltage generating characteristics of the PCGE with and without tip mass. The apparatus for the voltage generating test is illustrated in fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Experimental setup for voltage generating test with vibrator.

3.2 Voltage generating and charging battery test in wind tunnel

Fig.4 show the experimental set up for voltage generating test with wind speed 3.4 m/s for case A

(interface length of 1 mm) and 2.8 m/ s for the case B (interface length of 0.5 mm. for the battery charging test, we choose the nickel metal hydride battery with the voltage of 3.6V and the size of 40mAh.

Fig.4. Voltage generating and charging battery test in wind tunnel

4. Experiment Results

4.1 Voltage output performance with vibration test

Fig.5 shows the voltage output performance with the amplitude of excitation at $0.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m/ s}^2$, $2.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m/ s}^2$, and $4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m/ s}^2$. In case with tip mass, the PCGE has the low first resonant frequency at approximately 9.4 Hz

Fig.5. Voltage generating performance of the PCGE

4.2 Voltage output performance in wind tunnel test

Fig.6 shows the voltage output performance of the PCGE. At the frequency of 9.4 Hz, the peak voltage is 28 and 35 for the case A and B, respectively. The output voltage of the case B is generally larger than that of the case A.

4.3 Voltage output performance in wind tunnel test

Fig.7 shows the charge history of the 40mAh battery. We set the wind speed at 2.8 m/ s and the

interface length about 0.5 mm to enable the PCGE with tip mass to vibrate at its first natural frequency of 9.4 Hz and produce a voltage of 18 V for charging battery.

Fig.6. Voltage generating performance of the PCGE

Fig.7. Charge history of the 40mAh battery with resonant excitation of the PCGE

5. Conclusion

With the characteristics of the PCGE performed in the experiment results, we can see the application of PCGE in energy harvesting. The produced power can be stored in the battery for later use. With small size, the energy harvesting device can scavenge the wind energy in urban region.

References

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